

Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum

Meeting Summary – 29 January 2026

Introduction

The UK Health Data Research Alliance convened its sixth Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum on 29 January 2026. The meeting was co-chaired by Dr Macey Murray (Senior Research Fellow, MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL) and Dr Fiona Lugg-Widger (Director of Data, Centre for Trials Research, Cardiff University). Participants included trialists, researchers, data custodians, public representatives, funding organisations, and NHS and academic stakeholders.

Key objectives of the meeting were to:

- Understand the current status and direction of HDRS (including governance, scope and delivery approach).
- Review consultation feedback on the Forum's Green Paper and confirm next steps towards a White Paper.
- Share progress across the Transforming Data for Trials programme (routemap, training, case studies, public involvement).
- Gather input on future Forum priorities, with a focus on identifying actionable topics beyond data access.

Health Data Research Service (HDRS) update

Jen Boon (DHSC) [presented](#) an update on the Health Data Research Service (HDRS), outlining current policy direction, delivery approach, and early implementation priorities. Key highlights included:

- *Policy context and ambition:* HDRS was positioned as a major, politically backed investment in UK health data research infrastructure (including a commitment of up to £600m funding) and as part of wider government priorities across health improvement and life sciences growth.
- *Operating model:* HDRS is being set up as a separate government company, with DHSC acting as sponsor. HDRS leadership will have latitude to shape strategy and delivery, within broad expectations.
- *Expected capabilities (illustrative):* a single-entry approach to access and linkage across core national datasets (e.g., primary care, hospital, prescribing, deaths), support for linkage for consented research participants, broader data modalities (imaging/labs/pathology/genomics), and longer-term ambition to link across wider public datasets (in alignment with National Data Library direction).
- *Leadership appointments:* Chair Baroness Blackwood (announced 25 Nov 2025) and CEO Dr Melanie Iverson (announced 12 Jan 2026).

- *Near-term DHSC priorities*: incorporating HDRS as a company, securing approval of a business case/funding release, managing transition from the NHS England Research SDE Network as Data for R&D ends, and deepening four-nations working.
- *Discovery work to inform HDRS strategy*: workstreams included a “customer needs assessment”, analysis of the commercial landscape, and a Wellcome-led mapping of digital technology underpinning the UK health data ecosystem.

Group discussion points included:

- *National Data Library (NDL) relationship*: HDRS and NDL are both developing; HDRS is likely to function as the “health” component of a broader approach, but practical linkage/operating detail remains to be worked through.
- *Four-nations delivery*: the approach was described as genuinely four-nations (with learning from existing strengths), but with acknowledged policy/technical barriers (e.g., differing opt-out models). There was support for greater transparency on these barriers where possible.
- *Integration with existing programmes*: members asked for clarity on alignment and avoiding duplication of prior infrastructure work; DHSC agreed to take this away and return with a fuller response.
- *Public trust and past lessons*: contributors highlighted the importance of public involvement and clear framing (including that any charging model should be reinvested), noting trust failures create both ethical and practical risks.

Agreed direction: the Forum expressed strong interest in receiving a future update directly from HDRS leadership once the organisation is more fully established.

Green Paper consultation summary (Data access and consent)

Macey Murray [presented](#) a summary of consultation feedback on the Forum’s Green Paper on data access and consent for use of health systems data in clinical trials and proposed next steps toward a White Paper.

Consultation overview

The Green Paper was published on 20 October 2025 and consulted on for ~2 months, closing just before Christmas; 13 responses were received.

Respondents included clinical trialists (majority), public partners, health economists, a data custodian, a non-trials researcher, and a regulator/policymaker; most were England-based with representation also from Scotland and Northern Ireland.

Key findings

- Broad consensus that improving data access is essential to accelerating trials.
- Support for a centralised national data access approval system, emphasising: governance/accountability, transparent processes, meaningful public involvement, equity of access (academic and commercial), and adequate resourcing to prevent delays.
- Support for a national framework to standardise consent assessment, with preference for a short, practical framework building on existing guidance, anchored in public

benefit/trust/transparency; plus standardised wording for trial participants and UK-wide representation (public + data providers).

- More mixed views on precedent-set review pathways for common datasets (7 supportive; 5 unsure), suggesting a need for clearer worked examples (potentially in an appendix) in the next iteration.

Next step: The team will revise the Green Paper into a White Paper, aiming to publish by end March 2026, drawing on working group input.

Transforming Data for Trials programme updates

Macey Murray, Michelle Goonasekera (University of Oxford), Fiona Lugg-Widger, Rachel Copland (University of Dundee), and Nick Pitt (University of Oxford) [presented](#) updates across the Transforming Data for Trials programme, including the route map, training offer, case study catalogue, and public involvement.

Programme overview

The programme (established 2023) aims to transform access, utility, analysis and understanding of health systems data in trials, supported by a Trials Community Insight Group and a Public Advisory Group (PAG).

Updates included ongoing work on data utility (guidance + workshops; next workshop planned 21 May 2026 at UCL) and planned work on data integrity/provenance (workshops plus a Delphi process to refine a reporting framework).

Route map

A “routemap” is being developed to complement the NIHR clinical trials toolkit, providing stage-by-stage guidance for using health systems data in trials, informed by scoping, case examples and iterative review.

14 stations identified; 10 in development, 1 on hold, and 3 planned to start imminently. PAG input is being embedded via a dedicated PPI platform station and PPI checkpoints across stations. Target to go live is end of 2026 or early 2027.

Training

Training is being delivered as short “talking head” videos and modules aligned to the route map, hosted on the HDR UK Futures platform (free with login). Content includes introductory modules, data utility, building public trust, and short topic videos (some developed via internship programmes).

A key upcoming output is the Research Partners Hub (public-facing), co-produced with PAG members (including scripting and voice/video contributions).

Case study catalogue

A curated UK-wide catalogue of clinical trials using health systems data (e.g., recruitment, outcomes, pharmacovigilance), designed as a searchable/tagged learning resource capturing challenges, enablers, and practical advice.

Progress: 30+ trials approached; 11 confirmed; more expected later. A standard case study template has been finalised, and planned next steps include a site “beta” view and PAG review of how PPI is presented and interpreted.

Public Advisory Group

PAG currently has 22 members across all four nations, with 11 subgroup meetings held over the last year supporting training, route map review, and other programme outputs. Further work is underway to evidence and communicate PAG impact, including a further co-authored paper in development.

Emerging priorities and the Forum’s next focus area

Macey Murray and Fiona Lugg-Widger introduced a mentimeter survey to identify priority topics for future Forum meetings beyond data access (including suggestions for future speakers). Early discussion noted primary care data use as a persistent challenge.

- The survey would remain open for ~14 days, and members were encouraged to share it with colleagues to broaden input.
- The Forum reaffirmed a preference for topics where it can develop practical outputs (guidance/solutions), rather than operating solely as a discussion forum.

The next meeting was confirmed for 18 May 2026 ([sign-up via Eventbrite](#)) and is planned to run via Zoom.

Appendix

Contributing Organisations
Cardiff University
Department of Health & Social Care (DHSC)
Cystic Fibrosis Trust
Health Data Research UK (HDR UK)
Health Research Authority
Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA)
NHS England
Royal Marsden NHS Foundation Trust
Swansea University
Understanding Patient Data
University College London (UCL)
University of Dundee
University of Edinburgh
University of Oxford
University of Southampton